

D6.9

Pesticide analysis protocols and quality guidelines (oil)

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Deliverable 6.9 Pesticide analysis protocols and quality guidelines (oil)

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Executive Summary

D6.9 is the deliverable for task 6.5 “Evaluation of the presence of pesticide residues in olive oil from olive groves”. This document describes the status of the different olive groves in terms of pesticide presence. Pesticides (fungicides, herbicides and insecticides) may end up in the soil as a result of their use to protect the crops. Their identification and quantification may contribute to the development of programs for soil restoration, which, in the end, turn into the prevention of toxicological hazards.

The sampling protocol follows the same procedure as for pesticide residue analysis in olive oil. A total of 1.1 L of olive oil is required, divided into two 0.5 L glass bottles and one 0.1 L PET bottle. Ideally, olives should be collected entirely from orchards, but if not, random primary samples should be taken to ensure representativeness. Oil extraction should be done promptly using the Abencor® system, or olives should be frozen. Samples must be stored at 4°C, protected from light and heat, and shipped quickly to the UJA laboratory with proper packaging and documentation.

This document describes two analytical methods for this work: one multiresidue method including a list of 60 herbicides, fungicides, and insecticides; and a specific method for the analysis of the herbicide glyphosate and its main metabolite, aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA). For the internal validation of this methodology and quality assurance, the SANTE No 11312/2021 guidelines are followed. For the multiresidue determination of pesticides the procedure is carried out by adapting QuEChERS methodology to oil samples and using EMR-Lipid sorbent in the clean-up stage. The final solution is injected in the liquid chromatography tandem mass-spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) in electrospray ionization mode (ESI) both in positive and negative mode (ESI+, ESI-). As glyphosate and AMPA are not amenable to multiresidue methods due to their high polarity, and also are difficult to analyze because their interaction with glass surfaces and metals. Their analysis requires a specific method, so-called single-residue method. The methodology consists of a liquid-liquid extraction and then the supernatant is analyzed by LC-MS/MS using electrospray ionization in negative polarity mode (ESI-).

The data obtained from the analyzed samples will be used to establish a profile of pesticide residues in the different countries and across different soil management types (TD, HD, and ORG). The data obtained is used in conjunction with other variables to assess the agroecosystem functionality in the selected olive orchards. The ultimate goal is to understand the relationship between farming practices, soil health and olive oil quality and safety.

Table of Acronyms

Σ – Sum	MRL – Maximum residue level
\bar{x} – Mean value	MRM – Multiple reaction monitoring
ACN – Acetonitrile	MS – Mass spectrometry
AMPA – Aminomethylphosphonic acid	MS/MS – tandem mass spectrometry
d-SPE – Dispersive solid phase extraction	N – Number of points
ESI – Electrospray ionization mode	Na ₂ EDTA – Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid disodium salt dihydrate
FA – Formic Acid	NaCl – Sodium chloride
H ₃ PO ₄ –Phosphoric acid	PET – Polyethylene terephthalate
HAc – Acetic acid	PP – Polypropylene
HCl - Hydrochloric acid	PSA – Primary-secondary amine
HCO ₂ NH ₄ - Ammonium formate	PTFE – Polytetrafluoroethylene
HILIC – Hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography	QqQ – Triple quadrupole
HPLC – High Pressure Liquid Chromatography	QuEChERS – Quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged and safe
KH ₂ PO ₄ – Potassium dihydrogen phosphate	QuPPE – Quick Polar Pesticides
LLE – Liquid-liquid extraction	RSD – Relative standard deviation
LODs – Limits of detection	S – Standard deviation
LOQs – Limits of quantification	UAE – Ultrasound-assisted extraction
ME – Matrix Effects	UHPLC – Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography
MeOH – Methanol	
MgSO ₄ – Mangesium sulphate	Xi – Value in the data set

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This document is intended to be used by SOIL O-LIVE partners and, in a simplified version (the sampling protocol), by farmers involved in Tasks 6.5 and 6.6.

This protocol describes the procedure for the multiresidue determination of pesticides in oil samples. This procedure includes the sampling methodology, the sample treatment to extract and isolate the analytes from the olive oils and the quantification of the detected substances.

Considering the wide scope of the project and the high variability in the physicochemical properties of the pesticide residues that may be present in the olive oils, three analytical methods will be used. Each method will target a group of pesticide residues with similar chemical properties, which may include the active substances applied to the olive orchards and/or their transformation products.

The samples are extracted and purified previously to their analysis by chromatographic methods, using standard protocols for pesticide extraction (namely QuEChERS and QuPPE) adapted to oil samples. Finally, liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) is employed for the determination of the residues.

1.2 Definitions and abbreviations

1.2.1 Liquid-liquid extraction

Liquid–liquid extraction (LLE) or solvent extraction is a separation process based on the different distribution of the components to be separated (pesticides and other components of the sample) between two liquid phases. It depends on the mass transfer of the component to be extracted from the first liquid phase (oil sample) to the second one (e.g.: acetonitrile solvent).¹

In this procedure the sample is extracted by LLE using 10 mL ultrapure water containing 1 % of formic acid (1% FA) as extractant. The sample is vortexed to enhance the mass transference between the two phases. Then the mixture is centrifuged to accelerate the separation between both phases.

1.2.2 QuEChERS

QuEChERS methodology is the abbreviation for Quick, Easy, Cheap, Effective, Rugged and Safe. This extraction technique is simple and direct, involving an initial liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) or partitioning followed by a clean-up stage using dispersive solid-phase extraction (d-SPE).²

In the analytical procedure A (method A), for the multi-residue extraction of pesticides, the sample is homogenized with ultrapure water to make it more similar to other vegetable matrixes. Alternatively, the addition of water may be skipped and 2 g of oil may be directly extracted with acetonitrile, removing the residual fat by freezing out before the cleanup step. Pesticides are extracted with 10 mL of acidified acetonitrile with acetic acid (ACN 1% HAc), and

magnesium sulphate (MgSO_4) and sodium chloride (NaCl) salts are added to improve partitioning and obtain better pesticide recoveries in the extract.

The clean-up stage based on d-SPE typically uses PSA (primary secondary amine) and C18 solid phases.^{2,3} Based in the previous experience or our research group, the clean-up of the extracts will be performed by adding EMR-lipid (Enhanced Matrix Removal – lipid) sorbent, a commercial solid phase especially designed for the clean-up of fatty matrixes.⁴

1.2.3 Quick Polar Pesticides (QuPPE) method

The Quick Polar Pesticides (QuPPE) method is a quick method for the analysis of highly polar pesticides in food involving extraction with acidified methanol prior to analysis by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). This method is intended for very polar pesticides non amenable to common multiresidue methods such as QuEChERS.⁵

1.2.4 Pesticides

Pesticides are substances used in the agroindustry to protect plants and herbs from organisms or plant diseases by applying an active ingredient.⁶ The word *pesticide* covers a wide range of different products, such as herbicides, insecticides, fungicides, molluscicides, nematocides, and biocides.

In Europe, the Reg. No. 1107/2009 sets the standards and allows the commercialization of pesticides that do not directly harm life or the environment.⁷ Following that, a wide range of acaricides, herbicides, fungicides, insecticides, nematocides, repellents and plant growth repellents are analyzed in oils as due to plant uptake the pesticides present in soils can reach the plant, its fruits and, therefore, the oils produced with them. In this procedure, a selection of pesticides from different families is analyzed.

1.2.5 Maximum Residue Level (MRL)

A Maximum Residue Level (MRL) is the highest level of a pesticide residue that is legally tolerated in or on food or feed when pesticides are applied correctly (Good Agricultural Practice).⁸

The Regulation 396/2005 of the European Commission establishes harmonized MRLs in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin throughout the European Union.⁹ In Regulation 396/2005, MRLs are listed for pesticide/commodity combinations. An asterisk indicates that the MRL* is set at or about the LOQ with the LOQ being here a consensus figure rather than a measured value.¹⁰

1.2.6 Reversed-phase (RP) liquid chromatography

Liquid chromatography in which the mobile phase is significantly more polar than the stationary phase.¹¹ Typically, the stationary phase is a silica-based material with chemically bonded alkyl chains (e.g. C18). The mobile phase is a mixture of water and organic solvent (e.g.: methanol) in which the organic solvent is the strong eluent and increases its percentage during the analysis.

1.2.7 Hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography (HILIC)

Liquid chromatography in which the analytes are partitioned between a water-enriched layer, which is immobilized on a hydrophilic (polar) stationary phase, and a less-polar mobile phase, containing water and organic solvent.¹¹ A typical HILIC chromatographic column is filled with bare silica. Gradient elutions in HILIC start with a high percentage of organic solvent (weak eluent) and the amount of water (strong eluent) is increasing with the run time.

1.3 Material and equipment

Table 1. Materials and equipment

pH-meter	
Centrifuge	
PP tubes (50 and 15 mL)	
Filters	
Vortex	
Ultrapure water HPLC grade	
Glyphosate standard	CAS: 1071-83-6
AMPA standard	CAS: 1066-51-9
Isotopically labelled internal standard Glyphosate 1,2- ¹³ C ¹⁵ N (100 µg/mL)	CAS: 1185107-63-4
Isotopically labelled internal standard AMPA ¹³ C, ¹⁵ N (100 µg/mL)	CAS: 2727464-25-5
¹³ C ₃ -labelled caffeine standard	CAS: 78072-66-9
15 mL centrifuge tubes containing 1g of EMR-Lipid sorbent	Agilent P/N 5982-1010 (50 pack)
EMR-Lipid Polish 15 mL Tube containing 2 g MgSO ₄ /NaCl (4:1)	Agilent P/N 5982-0101 (50 pack)
Multi-residue pesticide standards	ANNEX 2
Sodium chloride (99.0 %)	CAS: 7647-14-5
Boric acid (99.5 %)	CAS: 10043-35-3
Magnesium sulphate (MgSO ₄)	CAS: 7487-88-9
Ammonium formate (HCO ₂ NH ₄)	CAS: 540-69-2
Hydrochloric acid (HCl)	CAS: 7647-01-0
Formic acid (HCO ₂ H) (98-100 %)	CAS: 64-18-6
Ammonium (NH ₃)	CAS: 7664-41-7
Acetic acid (HAc)	CAS: 64-19-7
Acetonitrile HPLC-grade	
Methanol HPLC-grade	
Ultra-high-pressure liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS/MS)	Dionex Ultimate 3000 HPLC (Thermo Scientific, San José, CA USA)
	Zorbax Rapid Resolution High Definition (RRHD) C18 UHPLC column (2.1 x 50 mm, 1.8 µm)
	Hypercarb column (100 × 2.1 mm i.d., 5 µm)

1.4 Analytical parameters and quality assurance of chromatographic methods

For the internal validation of this methodology and quality assurance, the SANTE No 11312/2021 guidelines are followed.¹⁰ Within-laboratory method validation should be performed to provide evidence that a method fits the intended purpose.

The analytical parameters for the methodology are characterized in terms of linearity, limits of detection (LODs) and limits of quantification (LOQs), matrix effect (ME), precision in terms of relative standard deviation (RSD) inter- and intraday, and trueness.

1.4.1 Calibration curves, LODs and LOQs

A calibration curve is prepared each time a batch of samples is analyzed by spiking blank oil samples (as blank matrix). To check the blank samples, they are analyzed in advance in triplicate.

A pesticide standard working solution (5 mg/L) is used to prepare the calibration curve. Consequently, seven different calibration points are prepared from 1 µg/kg to 2000 µg/kg.

Table 2. Calibration curve

Calibration point	Concentration (µg/kg)
P1	1
P2	10
P3	100
P4	500
P5	1000
P6	1500
P7	2000

LODs and LOQs are calculated as the minimum analyte concentration yielding a S/N equal to three and ten, respectively. Intra- and inter-day precision are tested for the methodology by spiking oil blank samples (n=9) at three different concentration levels 10, 500 and 1500 µg/kg, the samples are prepared and injected by triplicate on the same day or three consecutive days respectively.

The relative standard deviation expressed in % of peak areas should be calculated following the equation:

$$RSD = \left| \frac{S}{\bar{x}} \right| \cdot 100$$

Where:

S: standard deviation

\bar{x} : the mean value of the data set

The standard deviation should be calculated following this equation:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{N - 1}}$$

Where:

S: standard deviation

Σ: sum of

Xi: value in the data set

\bar{x} : the mean value of the data set

N: number of points in the data set

1.4.2 Recovery

For recovery studied homogenized samples are fortified with a determined concentration of analytes (100 µg/kg)

Recovery rates are calculated for each pesticide by means of interpolation of the areas integrated in the quantification peaks with the matrix-matched calibration curves.

If there is any dilution procedure during the study, it should be applied to the obtained values.

$$\text{Recovery (\%)} = \frac{\text{Conc spiked sample} - \text{Conc real sample}}{\text{Conc spiked sample}} \cdot 100$$

Where:

Conc. spiked sample: calculated concentration in spiked sample

Conc. real sample: concentration in real sample

1.4.3 Matrix effect

Matrix effect is calculated by comparing the slopes of matrix-matched calibration curves with those of external standard calibration curves using the following equation:⁹

$$\% \text{ matrix effect} = \left[\left(\frac{\text{slope of matrix - matched curve}}{\text{slope of in - solvent curve}} \right) - 1 \right] \times 100$$

The matrix effect classification was established according to the following criterion:¹² soft (0% to $\pm 20\%$), medium ($\pm 20\%$ to $\pm 50\%$), and strong (higher than $\pm 50\%$).

2. Sampling

The sampling protocol described in the present document is the same protocol described for analyzing pesticide residues in olive oil samples. **For all the analysis performed in the WP6 of the project, a total amount of 1.1 L of olive oil is required, separated into three different containers: two glass bottles of 0.5 L of capacity and one plastic bottle of 0.1 L of capacity.** Among plastics, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) satisfying food contact requirements is recommended.

The preferred option for the sampling is the total collection of the olives from the orchards, if possible. If there is no possibility, the sampling procedure applied should ensure that the global sample is representative of the lot. The sample will be a mixture of different portions of olives (primary samples) that should be taken at random at different points and depths from the container in which the olives have been collected. For olives which can be assumed to be distributed uniformly inside a lot, it is sufficient to take three primary samples (of 1.5 kg approx.) per lot to form the global sample of around 5 kg. Each global sample should be considered to be homogeneous in terms of analytical characteristics.^{13,14}

Olive oil should be extracted from fresh olives as fast as possible by means of an Abencor® system, following the procedure described in [section 2.1](#). If the extraction of oil cannot be done in the following 48h, the olives should be frozen until extraction. All the olive oil obtained by Abencor® should be mixed for homogenization and divided into three bottles: two amber glass bottles of 0.5 L and one PET bottle (amber color) of 0.1 L of capacity. The bottles should be like the one represented in Fig. 1 or equivalent.

Fig 1. PET/glass amber color bottle for oils. Source: SUNBOX webpage ([link](#))

Sample containers shall be clean and dry prior to use. Sampling shall be carried out in such a manner as to protect the samples from light and heat, avoiding contamination from extraneous material. The containers shall be almost completely filled; the little air space (headspace) shall not be too large, since air has a detrimental action on most fats (nitrogen flow should be applied if possible). Samples shall be protected from light and heat. They should be kept in the fridge (4 °C) and sent as soon as possible to the laboratory of analysis (UJA)^{1*}.

* To: Dr. Andrés J. Rascón López,
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The olive oil farm dispatches the packaged sample (3 bottles of the same olive oil sample) to the laboratory in charge of the analysis of the samples (UJA). **It is very important, especially in the case of glass bottles, to ensure to use a proper packaging to avoid breakage or sample loss during the shipment.** Insert in the package a printed document (sampling sheet) with the information of the sample (identification of the orchard, date of olives collection, olives storage conditions -if applicable-, date of olive oil extraction, oil yield %, olive oil storage conditions -if applicable-). This information should be also sent in a digital document (e.g., Word document).

The shipment of the samples to the laboratory has to be carried out in the shortest time possible by tracked expedition and the related cost will be paid by the farm which sends the samples.

** Note 1: for the shipment, we suggest specifying in the package description "Olive oil samples for scientific research purposes without any commercial values".*

****Note 2:** In case the extraction of olive oil by an Abencor® system is not available on-site, first-extraction virgin olive oil may be obtained in a mill, in similar conditions to those indicated in [Section 2.1](#). Malaxation of the olive paste should take place during 30 min and temperature should not exceed 30 °C. If the extraction conditions differ from these ones, they should be indicated in the sampling sheet (annex 2). In addition, the same extraction conditions should be used in the campaigns before and after the restoration, to obtain results suitable for comparison. Industrial oil yield% should be annotated in the sampling sheet.

The last option, which may be not suitable in due to the shipment costs, is to send to the laboratory an amount of olives enough to obtain approx. 1 L of olive oil in total by Abencor® system. Considering an industrial oil yield of 20% (a lower value is expected in the selected extraction conditions by Abencor®), 5 kg of frozen olives are required. The olives should be packed in materials chemically inert, if possible, and in a cold environment with dry ice.

2.1 Abencor conditions for extraction

Start by grinding a sample of at least 1 kg of olives in the crusher. Weigh 500 g of the obtained paste into each mixing jar and insert them in the Abencor® thermo-malaxator. It is possible to process simultaneously eight mixing jars. Malaxation will take place during 30 minutes without water addition and under controlled temperature. The bath temperature should be maintained at 30 °C.

If the paste emulsifies when malaxation begins, 1.7% talc may be added. An emulsified olive paste is fluid in texture and has a very uniform appearance, looking like a fruit purée. The oil does not float on the surface during malaxation, and the blades are always coated with olive paste. If this occurs and the malaxation take place with processing aids (talc), it should be indicated in the sampling sheet.

After the malaxation, the paste will be centrifuged for 2 min at 3500 rpm in the Abencor® centrifuge to separate the olive oil from solids. Collect the separated liquids (olive oil and water from the olive paste) in a 500-mL graduated glass cylinder and leave them to settle. After phase separation, read the volume of oil and convert it to weight for oil yield calculation. Finally, filter the extracted oils and pack them in three different bottles, as indicated previously.

$$\text{Oil yield(\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{mL olive oil} \cdot 0.915 \text{ g mL}^{-1}}{\text{g olive paste}} \right) \cdot 100$$

2.2 Sampling sheet template

When collecting and packing samples, it is important to keep accurate records of the process to ensure proper handling and analysis. To achieve this, all relevant information about the sample collection and packing should be documented and recorded in the table existing in ANNEX 1. This table should include details such as the date and time of the sample collection, the location of the collection, and any specific handling or packing instructions. Having this information in a clear and organized format allows for easy reference and ensures that all necessary steps are taken to maintain the integrity of the sample.

2.3 Sample reception in the laboratory

At the reception of the samples, the laboratory is responsible for:

- Checking the integrity of the shipped bottles. In case of breakages or leakages, the farmers should be contacted, and a new shipment should be arranged.
- Checking that all the information required in Annex 2 has been filled in by the farmers for each sample. If some information is missing, they should immediately ask the farmers.
- Storing the sample information, protecting the identity of the olive oil farm according to the confidentiality agreement.
- Building an Excel sheet with correct equivalence between the sample name given by the farmer and the unique sample code to be used in the laboratory.

3. Procedure

The samples should be remixed in the laboratory using mechanical movements until visually homogeneous. Six different aliquots should be taken from each sample.^{4,13,14} Aliquots 1-4 will be obtained from olive oil stored in glass bottles, while aliquots 5 and 6 will be taken from olive oil packages in plastic bottle.

- Aliquot 1 & 2: 10 g of olive oil for the multi-residue analysis (Method A)
- Aliquot 3 & 4: 10 g of olive oil for high-polar pesticide analysis (Method B)
- Aliquot 5 & 6: 10 g of olive oil for glyphosate and AMPA analysis (Method C)

Analysis of these sample aliquots will be carried out following the sample treatment and the chromatographic conditions described in the corresponding method (A, B or C).

3.1 Reagents and solutions

- Pesticides standards in ACN
- Surrogate standards (Isotopically labeled internal standards) in ACN
- Glyphosate and AMPA standard in water
- Glyphosate and AMPA surrogate standard in water
- Ultrapure water HPLC-grade
- MgSO₄
- HCOOH (FA)
- 15 mL centrifuge tubes containing 1g of EMR-lipid sorbent
- EMR-Lipid Polish 15 mL Tube containing 2 g MgSO₄/NaCl (4:1)
- NaCl (99 %)
- ACN (1 % HAc)
- ACN (0.1 % FA)
- 100 mM Ammonium formate (pH 2.85, adjusted with HAc)
- Ultrapure water (1 % FA)
- Water:MeOH:HAc (94:5:1, v/v/v)
- MeOH (1 % HAc)

3.2 Method A. Multi-residue determination of pesticides

3.2.1 QuEChERS extraction protocol for olive oil samples

This procedure is carried out by adapting QuEChERS methodology to oil samples and using EMR-Lipid sorbent in the clean-up stage.⁴

1. Place 10 g of homogenized sample (3 g of fat + 7 mL ultrapure water) in a 50 mL PP centrifuge tube
2. Add 100 µL of the surrogate standards mix
3. Add 10 mL of ACN (1% HAc), 4 g of MgSO₄ and 1 g of NaCl
4. Shake for 1 min
5. Activate the EMR-Lipid sorbent (1 g) with 5 mL of ultrapure water in a PP tube
6. Add 5 mL extract from the sample partitioning and shake for 1 min
7. Centrifuge for 5 min (5000 rpm)
8. Transfer 5 mL of supernatant to a PP tube with 1.6 g of MgSO₄ and 0.4 g of NaCl (EMR-Lipid Polish tube)
9. Shake and centrifuge again (5 min, 5000 rpm)
10. Dilution of the extract 1:10 with ultrapure water
11. Filter the final extract

The final solution is injected in the liquid chromatography tandem mass-spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) in electrospray ionization mode (ESI) both in positive and negative mode (ESI+, ESI-).

3.2.2 Reverse phase (RP) LC-MS/MS analysis

All the vials from sample treatment and calibration curves should be placed in the UHPLC-MS/MS system and analyzed following the conditions addressed in UHPLC-MS/MS procedure below.

- **UHPLC conditions**

This procedure is set for the Dionex Ultimate 3000 HPLC (Thermo Scientific, San José, CA USA) packed with Zorbax Rapid Resolution High Definition (RRHD) C18 UHPLC column (2.1 mm i.d. x 50 mm, 1.8 µm).

Table 3. Eluents for UHPLC

Eluent A	Eluent B
Formic acid 0.1% in ultrapure water	Formic acid 0.1% ACN

The eluents should be prepared fresh each run.

- The column oven set at 25 °C

- Flow rate set at 0.3 mL/min
- Injection volume 10 µL

The gradient program for the separation is as follows:

Table 4. Gradient program for separation (UHPLC)

Time (min)	Eluent A (%)	Eluent B (%)	Flow (mL/min)
0	95	5	0.3
5	0	5	0.3
18	0	100	0.3
20	0	100	0.3
21	95	5	0.3

The system should be equilibrated 5 min after each run.

- **MS/MS settings**

The TSQ Quantiva triple quadrupole (QqQ) from Thermo Scientific (USA), fitted with a heated electrospray ionization probe (HESI) in positive ionization mode is employed for the analysis.

The analytes are identified with chromatographic characteristics and multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) specific fragmentation. Data are processed with XCalibur software Version 3.0.63

The predicted MRM transitions available in the mass library NIST¹⁵ and Drugbank¹⁶ for a preliminary list of selected compounds are included in ANNEX 3, Table 1. MRM transitions and collision energy (V) should be adjusted empirically for each compound. The list of compounds may be modified during method development and validation.

3.3 Method B. Multi-residue extraction of highly-polar pesticides

3.3.1 QuPpe extraction protocol for olive oil samples

This procedure is carried out by adapting QuPpe methodology to oil samples.^{5,17}

1. Place 10 g of homogenized sample in a 50 mL PP centrifuge tube
2. Add 100 µL of the surrogate standards
3. Add 10 mL of MeOH (1% FA) and 10 mL of ultrapure water
4. Shake for 1 min
5. Heat the sample for 15 min at 80 °C
6. After cooling down, shake the tube again for 1 min
7. Centrifuge for 3 min (3500 rpm)
8. Transfer 1 mL of supernatant to a PP tube and dilute with 4 mL ACN (0.1 % FA)
9. Shake and centrifuge again (3 min, 3500 rpm)
10. Filter the final extract through 0.45 µm pore diameter PTFE filter

The final solution is injected in the liquid chromatography tandem mass-spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) in electrospray ionization mode (ESI) both in positive and negative mode (ESI+, ESI-).

3.3.2 Hydrophilic interaction liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (HILIC-MS/MS) analysis

All the vials from sample treatment and calibration curves should be placed in the UHPLC-MS/MS system and analyzed following the conditions addressed in UHPLC-MS/MS procedure below.

- **UHPLC conditions**

This procedure is set for the Dionex Ultimate 3000 HPLC (Thermo Scientific, San José, CA USA) packed with Agilent Zorbax Rapid Resolution High Definition (RRHD) HILIC Plus column (2.1 mm×100 mm, 1.8 µm particle size)

Table 5. Eluents for HILIC-MS/MS analysis

Eluent A	Eluent B
100 mM Ammonium formate (pH 2.85, adjusted with FA)	ACN (0.1% FA)

The eluents should be prepared fresh each run.

- The column oven set at 25 °C
- Flow rate set at 0.2 mL/min
- Injection volume 10 µL

The gradient program for the separation is as follows:

Table 6. Gradient program for separation in HILIC-MS/MS analysis

Time (min)	Eluent A (%)	Eluent B (%)	Flow (mL/min)
0	10	90	0.2
10	20	80	0.2
13	60	40	0.3
16	60	40	0.3
18	10	90	0.2

The system should be equilibrated 5 min after each run.

- **MS/MS settings**

The TSQ Quantiva triple quadrupole (QqQ) from Thermo Scientific (USA), fitted with a heated electrospray ionization probe (HESI) in positive ionization mode is employed for the analysis.

The analytes are identified with chromatographic characteristics and multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) specific fragmentation. Data are processed with XCalibur software Ver. 3.0.63

The tentative MRM transitions for highly polar pesticides are in ANNEX 3, Table 2.

****Important note²:** The use of plastic volumetric flasks and vials is highly recommended, as several of **the compounds covered by this method (e.g. Paraquat, Diquat) tend to interact with glass-surfaces**. Such interactions with glass surfaces are typically more pronounced in solutions consisting of aprotic solvents (e.g. acetonitrile). Increasing water content and/or acidity typically reduces such interactions. Percent losses due to such interactions are typically higher at low concentrations.

3.4 Method C. Glyphosate and AMPA determination

These two pesticides (glyphosate and its metabolite) are compounds not amenable to multiresidue methods due to their high polarity, and also are difficult to analyze because their interaction with glass surfaces and metals. Therefore, their analysis requires a specific method, so-called single-residue method.

3.4.1 LLE protocol for olive oil samples

In this procedure, a LLE is performed, as follows:¹⁸

- In a 50 mL PP tube, place 10 g of homogenized olive oil sample that has been stored in the plastic bottle (*see important note in the text box at the end of the protocol*)
- Add 100 µL of the surrogate standards
- Add 10 mL of acidified ultrapure water (1 % FA)
- Shake for 1 min
- Centrifuge for 10 min (3700 rpm)
- Filter 1 mL of supernatant through 0.45 µm filter

The supernatant is analyzed by LC-MS/MS using electrospray ionization in negative polarity mode (ESI-).

3.4.2 LC-MS/MS analysis

All the vials from sample treatment and calibration curves should be placed in the UHPLC-MS/MS system and analyzed following the conditions addressed in UHPLC-MS/MS procedure below.

- **UHPLC conditions¹⁸**

This procedure is set for the Dionex Ultimate 3000 HPLC (Thermo Scientific, San José, CA USA) packed with Hypercarb column (100 × 2.1 mm i.d., 5 µm particle size).

Table 7. Eluents for LC-MS/MS analysis

Eluent A	Eluent B
MeOH (1 % HAc)	water:MeOH:HAc (94:5:1, v/v/v)

The eluents should be prepared fresh each run.

- The column oven should be set at 25 °C.
- Flow rate set at 0.4 mL/min
- Injection volume 5 µL

The gradient program for the separation is as follows:

Table 8. Gradient program for separation in LC-MS/MS analysis

Time (min)	Eluent A (%)	Eluent B (%)	Flow (mL/min)
0	0	100	0.4
5	30	70	0.4
6	30	70	0.4
7	90	10	0.4
8	90	10	0.4
10	0	100	0.4

The system should be equilibrated 5 min after each run.

- **MS/MS settings**

The TSQ Quantiva triple quadrupole (QqQ) from Thermo Scientific (USA), fitted with a heated electrospray ionization probe (HESI) in positive ionization mode is employed for the analysis.

The analytes are identified with chromatographic characteristics and multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) specific fragmentation. Data are processed with XCalibur software Ver. 3.0.63

The predicted MRM transitions for glyphosate and AMPA available in the mass library NIST¹⁵ and Drugbank¹⁶ for each compound are the listed in ANNEX 3, Table 3.

****Important note²:** The use of plastic volumetric flasks and vials is highly recommended, as **the compounds covered by this method (e.g. Glyphosate) tend to interact with glass-surfaces**. Such interactions with glass surfaces are typically more pronounced in solutions consisting of aprotic solvents (e.g. acetonitrile). Increasing water content and/or acidity typically reduces such interactions. Percent losses due to such interactions are typically higher at low concentrations.

4. Expression of results

The concentration of each compound is obtained from the calibration curve equation. Typically, the equation is as follows:

$$\text{Area} = K \cdot [\text{compound}] + b$$

Where:

Area: area of each compound extracted from the chromatogram

K: slope of the curve

[compound]: compound concentration in $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$

b: intercept

The concentration is calculated using the aforementioned equation if the correlation factor (r) is over 0.995.

Dilution steps should be taken into account for the calculation and the concentration should be expressed as micrograms of the detected pesticide residue per kilogram of olive oil sample.

The concentration is calculated for each replicate, reporting the mean value of the results (\bar{x}). The standard deviation (S) should be added to the result. Therefore, the final concentration should be presented as follows:

$$[\text{Compound}] = \bar{x} \pm S \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$$

The mean value obtained for a pesticide will be compared to the MRL in force in the European Union.¹⁹

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ANNEX 2: Pesticides standards and surrogates.

Table 1. Pesticide standards

Pesticide	CAS	Pesticide	CAS
2,4-DB	94-82-6	Heptachlor	76-44-8
Abamectin	71751-41-2	Heptachlor endo epoxide (iso A)	1024-57-3
Aldrin	309-00-2	Heptachlor epoxide (iso B)	
AMPA	1066-51-9	Imazalil	35554-44-0
Atrazine	1912-24-9	Imazamox	114311-32-9
Atrazine-deisopropyl	6190-65-4	Imidacloprid	138261-41-3
Atrazine-desethyl	1007-28-9	Indoxacarb	173584-44-6
Azoxystrobin	131860-33-8	Isoproturon	34123-59-6
Bentazone	25057-89-0	Isoxaben	82558-50-7
Bixafen	581809-46-3	Lenacil	1/8/64
Boscalid	188425-85-6	Linuron	330-55-2
Bromuconazole	116255-48-2	Malathion	121-75-5
Carbaryl	63-25-2	MCPA	94-74-6
Carbendazim	10605-21-7	Metalaxyl	57837-19-1
Carbofuran	1563-66-2	Metamitron	41394-05-2
Carbofuran, -3-hydroxy	16655-82-6	Metconazole	125116-23-6
Carbofuran, -keto	16709-30-1	Metolachlor	51218-45-2
Chlordane cis- (alpha)	12789-03-6	Metrafenone	220899-03-6
Chlordane trans- (gamma)	5103-74-2	Myclobutanil	88671-89-0
Chlordecone	143-50-0	Parathion	56-38-2
Chlorfenvinphos	470-90-6	Parathion-methyl	298-00-0
Chloridazon	1698-60-8	Penconazole	66246-88-6
Chlorpyrifos	2921-88-2	Pendimethalin	40487-42-1
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	5598-13-0	Penflufen	494793-67-8
Clothianidin	210880-92-5	Pentachlorbenzene	608-93-5
Cymoxanil	57966-95-7	Penthiopyrad	183675-82-3
Cyproconazole	94361-06-5	Pinoxaden	243973-20-8
Cyprodinil	121552-61-2	Pirimicarb	23103-98-2
DDD o,p'	72-54-8	Pirimiphos-methyl	29232-93-7
DDD p,p'	72-54-8	Prochloraz	67747-09-5
DDE o,p'	72-55-9	Procymidone	32809-16-8
DDE p,p'	72-55-9	Triadimenol	55219-65-3
DDT o,p'	50-29-3	Tri-allate	2303-17-5
DDT p,p'	50-29-3	Triclopyr	55335-06-3
Deltamethrin	52918-63-5	Trifloxystrobin	141517-21-7
Diazinon	333-41-5	Promethryn	7287-19-6
Dieldrin	60-57-1	Propiconazole	60207-90-1
Difenoconazole	119446-68-3	Prosulfocarb	52888-80-9
Diflufenican	83164-33-4	Prothioconazole desthio	120983-64-4
Dimethenamid-P	163515-14-8	Phthalimide	85-41-6
Dimethomorph	110488-70-5	Pyraclostrobin	175013-18-0
Dimoxystrobin	149961-52-4	Pyriofenone	688046-61-9
Diuron	330-54-1	Quinoxifen	124495-18-7
Endosulfan alpha-	959-98-8	Simazine	122-34-9
Endosulfan beta-	33213-65-9	Tebuconazole	107534-96-3
Endosulfan sulphate	1031-07-8	Terbutylazine	5915-41-3
Endrin	72-20-8	Terbutylazine-desethyl	30125-63-4
Epoxiconazole	133855-98-8	Terbutryn	886-50-0
Ethion	563-12-2	Thiabendazole	148-79-8
Fenbuconazole	114369-43-6	Thiamethoxam	153719-23-4
Fenpropidin	67306-00-7	Thiophanate-methyl	23564-05-8
Fenpropimorph	67564-91-4		
Fluazinam	79622-59-6		
Fludioxonil	131341-86-1		
Flufenacet	142459-58-3		
Fluometuron	2164-17-2		
Fluopicolide	239110-15-7		
Fluopyram	658066-35-4		
Fluoxastrobin	361377-29-9		
Fluquinconazole	136426-54-5		
Fluroxypyr	69377-81-7		
Folpet	133-07-3		
Glyphosate	1071-83-6		
hexachlorobenzene	118-74-1		

ANNEX 3: Pesticides MRM data.

Table 1. Predicted MRM transitions for a preliminary list of multiresidue pesticides.

Pesticide	CAS	IONIZATION MODE	Mass (m/z)	Precursor ion (m/z)	Quantification peak (m/z)	Confirmation peak (m/z)
Abamectin	71751-41-2	ESI +	1732.1	1733.1	890.5	567.4
Atrazine	1912-24-9	ESI +	215.68	216.101	170.104	128.056
		ESI -		168.089	125.083	83.061
Atrazine-deisopropyl	1007-28-9	ESI +	173.60	174.054	216.101	104.003
Atrazine-desethyl	6190-65-4	ESI +	187.63	188.069	190.065	146.021
		ESI -		186.055	150.078	188.053
Azoxystrobin	131860-33-8	ESI +	403.4	404.124	372.098	373.101
Bentazone	25057-89-0	ESI +	240.28	241.064	199.016	200.017
		ESI -		239.049	132.032	133.041
Bixafen	581809-46-3	ESI +	414.2	N/A ^a	N/A	N/A
Boscalid	188425-85-6	ESI +	343.2	343.039	343.04	345.036
Bromuconazole	116255-48-2	ESI +	377.1	375.961	158.976	70.04
Carbaryl	63-25-2	ESI +	201.22	202.086	145.063	146.067
Carbendazim	10605-21-7	ESI +	191.19	192.077	160.048	132.055
		ESI -		190.062	158.035	126.030
Carbofuran	1563-66-2	ESI +	221.25	222.113	165.091	123.044
Carbofuran, -3-hydroxy	16655-82-6	ESI +	237.25	238.107	181.086	163.075
Carbofuran, -keto	16709-30-1	ESI +	235.24	N/A	N/A	N/A
Chloridazon	1698-60-8	ESI +	221.64	222.042	224.039	223.045
Chlorpyrifos	2921-88-2	ESI +	350.6	349.933	114.961	197.928
Chlorpyrifos-methyl	5598-13-0	ESI +	322.5	321.902	289.876	124.982
Clothianidin	210880-92-5	ESI +	249.68	250.016	169.054	131.967
Cymoxanil	57966-95-7	ESI +	198.18	219.112	132.080	133.088
Cyproconazole	94361-06-5	ESI +	291.77	292.121	291.117	294.117
Cyprodinil	121552-61-2	ESI +	225.29	226.134	209.106	133.074
Diazinon	333-41-5	ESI +	304.35	305.108	169.079	153.102
Difenoconazole	119446-68-3	ESI +	406.3	406.072	186.051	206.080
Diflufenican	83164-33-4	ESI +	394.3	395.080	266.042	375.074
Dimethomorph	110488-70-5	ESI +	387.9	388.131	301.062	165.054
Dimoxystrobin	149961-52-4	ESI +	326.4	327.170	205.097	206.099
Diuron	330-54-1	ESI +	233.09	233.024	72.044	159.971
		ESI -		231.010	185.952	149.975
Epoxiconazole	133855-98-8	ESI +	329.8	330.080	121.044	123.024
Ethion	563-12-2	ESI +	384.5	384.994	199.000	170.968
Fenbuconazole	114369-43-6	ESI +	336.8	337.121	70.039	125.014
Fenpropidin	67306-00-7	ESI +	273.5	274.252	275.255	276.258
Fenpropimorph	67564-91-4	ESI +	303.5	304.263	147.115	306.27
Fluazinam	79622-59-6	ESI -	465.09	462.944	397.977	415.943
Fludioxonil	131341-86-1	ESI -	248.18	247.032	181.040	180.032
Flufenacet	142459-58-3	ESI +	363.33	364.073	194.096	364.073
Fluometuron	2164-17-2	ESI +	232.20	233.089	72.044	213.083
Fluopyram	658066-35-4		396.71	N/A	N/A	N/A
Fluoxastrobin	361377-29-9	ESI+	458.8	459.086	427.060	188.038
Fluquinconazole	136426-54-5	ESI+	376.2	376.017	162.970	306.981
Fluroxypyr	69377-81-7	ESI+	255.03	254.973	236.962	208.968
Imazalil	35554-44-0	ESI+	297.2	298.058	297.056	299.052
Imazamox	114311-32-9	ESI+	305.33	306.144	264.098	261.123
Imidacloprid	138261-41-3	ESI+	255.66	256.059	256.059	209.058
Indoxacarb	173584-44-6	ESI+	527.8	528.078	530.075	529.081
Isoproturon	34123-59-6	ESI+	206.28	207.149	208.151	165.101
Isoxaben	82558-50-7	ESI+	332.4	333.180	165.053	334.184
Lenacil	2164-08-1	ESI+	234.29	235.144	153.065	236.146
Linuron	330-55-2	ESI+	249.09	249.019	251.016	182.023
Malathion	121-75-5	ESI-	330.4	329.028	124.983	94.936
MCPA	94-74-6	ESI-	200.62	199.016	141.011	199.016
Metalaxyl	57837-19-1	ESI+	279.33	280.154	220.132	248.127
Metamitron	41394-05-2	ESI-	202.21	201.078	117.034	185.058
Metconazole	125116-23-6	ESI+	319.8	320.152	322.149	321.155
Metolachlor	51218-45-2	ESI+	283.79	284.141	252.115	254.112
Metrafenone	220899-03-6	ESI+	409.3	409.064	226.970	194.057
Myclobutanil	88671-89-0	ESI+	288.77	289.121	291.118	290.124
Parathion	56-38-2	ESI+	291.26	292.040	235.977	264.008
Parathion-methyl	298-00-0	ESI+	263.21	264.009	265.011	249.993
Penconazole	66246-88-6	ESI+	284.18	284.071	70.039	158.976
Pendimethalin	40487-42-1	ESI+	281.31	282.144	212.066	213.068

Penflufen	494793-67-8	ESI+	317.4	N/A	N/A	N/A
Penthiopyrad	183675-82-3	ESI+	359.4	N/A	N/A	N/A
Pinoxaden	243973-20-8	ESI+	400.5	401.243	317.185	N/A
Pirimicarb	23103-98-2	ESI+	238.29	239.150	182.127	195.159
Pirimiphos-methyl	29232-93-7	ESI+	305.34	306.103	164.116	307.106
Prochloraz	67747-09-5	ESI+	376.7	378.035	308.000	309.997
Procyimidone	32809-16-8	ESI+	284.13	284.024	256.029	67.054
Triadimenol	55219-65-3	ESI+	295.76	296.116	227.081	296.114
Tri-allate	2303-17-5	ESI+	304.7	305.011	304.009	261.961
Triclopyr	55335-06-3	ESI+	256.5	255.933	237.922	209.927
Trifloxystrobin	141517-21-7	ESI+	408.4	409.137	186.052	116.049
Promethryn	7287-19-6	ESI+	241.36	242.143	200.096	158.049
Propiconazole	60207-90-1	ESI+	342.2	342.076	158.976	69.069
Prosulfocarb	52888-80-9	ESI+	251.39	252.141	128.106	254.138
Prothioconazole desthio	120983-64-4	ESI+	312.2	313.069	312.066	314.063
Pyraclostrobin	175013-18-0	ESI+	387.8	388.105	194.080	390.103
Pyriofenone	688046-61-9	ESI+	365.8	N/A	N/A	N/A
Quinoxifen	124495-18-7	ESI+	308.1	308.004	310.001	196.978
Simazine	122-34-9	ESI+	201.66	202.085	145.063	146.066
Tebuconazole	107534-96-3	ESI+	307.82	308.152	310.149	151.029
Terbutylazine	5915-41-3	ESI+	229.71	230.116	232.113	174.053
Terbutylazine-desethyl	30125-63-4	ESI+	201.66	202.085	146.022	204.082
Terbutryn	886-50-0	ESI+	241.36	242.143	186.080	187.082
Thiabendazole	148-79-8	ESI+	201.25	202.043	175.033	131.060
Thiamethoxam	153719-23-4	ESI+	291.72	292.026	211.064	210.057
Thiophanate-methyl	23564-05-8	ESI+	342.4	343.052	311.026	151.031

^aN/A: not available

Table 2. MRM transitions for highly polar pesticides, according to scientific literature.¹²

Pesticide	CAS	IONIZATION MODE	Mass (m/z)	Precursor ion (m/z)	Quantification peak (m/z)	Confirmation peak (m/z)
Amitrole	61-82-5	ESI +	85.0	85.2	43.4	57.3
Cyromazine	66215-27-8	ESI +	167.1	167.1	85.3	68.3
Diquat	2764-72-9	ESI +	183.1	183.1	157.2	78.2
Paraquat	4685-14-7	ESI +	171.1	171.1	77.3	155.1
Mepiquat	15302-91-7	ESI +	114.1	114.2	98.2	58.4
Trimesium	81591-81-3	ESI +	77.0	77.2	62.3	47.4
Fosetyl-aluminium	39148-24-8	ESI -	109.0	109.1	81.3	63.2

Table 3. Predicted MRM transitions for glyphosate and AMPA.

Pesticide	CAS	IONIZATION MODE	Mass (m/z)	Precursor ion (m/z)	Quantification peak (m/z)	Confirmation peak (m/z)
Glyphosate	1071-83-6	ESI -	169.07	167.8	63	79
AMPA	1066-51-9	ESI -	111.04	110	81.2	62.9

ANNEX 4: Report template

Report XXXXXX/2023

No of pages: XXXX

Reception date:

Starting date:

Finishing date:

Report elaborated by:

Test

Multiresidue method for the determination of pesticides in oils

Samples

1. Sample name
 - a. Sample code

Test Method

Multiresidue method for the determination of pesticides in oils

Sum of identified substances					
Remarks					

Table 2

Sample	Pesticides		
	Number of pesticides detected	Highest concentration (mg/kg)	Sum (mg/kg)
Sample name Code XXXX			